

Coverage of DOAJ journals' citations through OpenCitations (Data Management Plan)

Version 4

Funder
None

Grant
None

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Bologna

Datasets

Title: [Dataset for Coverage of DOAJ journals' citations through OpenCitations](#)

Template: [Horizon 2020](#)

The dataset contains the results of our research on the coverage of DOAJ journals' citations through OpenCitations. More specifically, it contains JSON files extracted from operations at each step of the workflow.

The dataset contains:

- **by_journal.json**: a file containing all information extracted by Open Citations about DOAJ journals divide by year and journal name. Inside the file, the metadata about the journal are:

ISSN

EISSN

number of articles overall in the journal

subject(s)

number of citations received

number of citations done

ratio between citations done and received

number of citations received from DOAJ journals

number of citations done to DOAJ journals

ratio between citations done to and received from DOAJ journals.

- **normal.json**: a file containing all information extracted from Open Citations about DOAJ journals divided only by year. Inside the file, the data by year are:

number of citations received.

number of citations done.

ratio between citations done and received.

number of self-citations made by DOAJ inside Open Citations.

ratio between the self-citation and the total citations received and done by DOAJ.

- **errors.json**: a file containing the count of all errors obtained from computations. Inside the file:

errors about records that don't have any specified date (null dates).

errors about records that have impossible dates (wrong dates).

errors about articles that don't have any specified Dois.

errors about Open Citations records that don't have any Dois in the citing or cited fields.

- **DOAJ_metrics.json**: a file containing metrics about DOAJ and Open Citations, obtained by computations. Inside the file are these fields:

number of journals with dois.

number of articles which have been processed during computations.

number of used Dois. All dois (with no repetition) which are used for the adding journal operation.

number of repeated Dois. All dois which are repeated inside the same or in another journal.

number of accepted Dois. All articles (with repetition) which have both a defined journal and a defined doi.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To combine with other data

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- derived or compiled (e.g.
- text mining
- 3D models)

Secondary data after extraction and analysis from OpenCitations and DOAJ data.

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files
- Numerical
- Specimen collections

The collected data are extracted from CSV files, with data in numerical and string formats.

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

Yes

<https://opencitations.net/index/coci>, <https://doaj.org/docs/public-data-dump/>

- To compare and combine with other data
- To follow-up research on a specific area

2.1.2 Where do the described data reside?

- a. GitHub
- b. Zenodo

2.1.3 Which data will be re-used?

- a. DOAJ journals public data dump (May 07, 2022)
- b. OpenCitations public data dump (March 2022)
- c. DOAJ articles public data dump (May 01, 2022)

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

We specify the metadata for our datasets through [Zenodo](#), which uses the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#).

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

[DataCite Metadata Schema](#).

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

All of our datasets' metadata will be openly and freely published in Zenodo.

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snake_case

We used the Snak case naming convention, where the first letter of each word is written in lowercase and space is replaced with an underscore character (_). Example: doi_with_count.json

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Every version of our project is published in Zenodo with a version number.

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Every version of our project is published in Zenodo with a unique DOI.

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

OpenAIRE

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

JSON Data Interchange Format

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

.json is a non-proprietary format.

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Any open source editor can be used to open .json format.

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

Other

Zenodo

GitHub repository

<https://github.com/open-sci/2021-2022-don-t-lock-up-code>

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

[Zenodo](#) and [Github](#) use versioning, allowing for backup and recovery.

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

3.1.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

immediately

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

Yes

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

The dataset will be published in Github together with instructions on how to access it and the *Issue* forum up for anyone who has any doubt.

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

All of the researchers are data managers.

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

- a. Constance Dami (orcid:0000-0003-4819-3975)
- b. Chiara Manca (orcid:0000-0003-4037-1175)
- c. Umut Kucuk (orcid:0000-0002-6352-2215)
- d. Alessandro Bertozzi (orcid:0000-0003-0933-4640)

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Other
- Personal Archive

GitHub repository

The data will be stored on a Github repository as well as in Zenodo, with local copies for the researchers.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [Software for Coverage of DOAJ journals' citations through OpenCitations](#)

Template: [Horizon 2020](#)

This dataset contains the software used for our research.

This code processes the public data dumps from [DOAJ](#) and [OpenCitations](#). We used the data dump of DOAJ articles of May 01, 2022, and the data dump of DOAJ journals of May 07, 2022. For Open Citations data, we used the COCI dump of March 2022.

The [Python](#) script uses libraries such as [Pandas](#), [Tarfile](#), and [Plotly](#) for gathering, manipulating, analyzing, and visualizing the data of this research.

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- To obtain information
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1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- reference or canonical (e.g.
- static
- peer-reviewed data sets
- likely published or curated
- such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Software

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

KB (kilobyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

Yes

<https://pandas.pydata.org/>, <https://docs.python.org/3/library/os.html>,
<https://docs.python.org/3/library/glob.html>,
<https://docs.python.org/3/library/json.html>,
<https://docs.python.org/3/library/pickle.html>,
<https://docs.python.org/3/library/tarfile.html>, <https://plotly.com/>,
<https://docs.python.org/3/library/zipfile.html>,
<https://docs.python.org/3/library/io.html>

To develop new products/ services

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3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

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3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

a. <https://peps.python.org/pep-0008/>

We used PEP 8 for writing the code, following conventions used by the Python community (e.g. 4 spaces per indentation level, utf-8 for encoding, etc.)

b. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snake_case

We used the Snake case convention for naming the files, starting each word with a lowercase and replacing spaces with underscore (_). Example: `create_json_dois.py`

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Python Script File

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

.py and .ipynb are non-proprietary formats.

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Any free open source editor can be used to open the software.

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

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3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

immediately

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

MIT License

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

Yes

We will provide testing together with the code that we will produce.

3.1.4.6 Please provide URL with the documented procedures

<https://docs.python.org/3/library/unittest.html>

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

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GitHub repository, Zenodo

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